

Studies on Indian Medicinal Plants-Part XXIX¹ Diterpenoid and Other Constituents of *Enhydra fluctuans* Lour.

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The petroleum ether extract of *Enhydra fluctuans* Lour. (Compositae) yielded three new diterpenoids, namely, 17-hydroxy-(-)-kaur-15-en-19-oic acid, 15 α -isovaleroyloxy- and 15 α -angeloyloxy-(-)-kaur-16-en-19-oic acid, in addition, to the known (-)-kaur-16-en-19-oic acid, (-)-kaur-15-en-19-oic acid, (-)-kauran-16 α -ol, 16 α -hydroxy-(-)-kauran-19-oic acid and 15 α -hydroxy-(-)-kaur-16-en-19-oic acid. The steroidal components isolated are, stigmasterol, 4, 22-stigmastadien-3-one, (24S)-24-ethyl-5, 22, 25-cholestatrien-3 β -ol and the hitherto unreported (24S)-24-ethyl-5, 22, 25-cholestatrien-3 β -yl stearate and (24S)-24-ethyl-4, 22, 25-cholestatrien-3-one. The other compounds isolated are, β -amyrin, myricyl alcohol and myristic acid and the three sesquiterpene lactones reported earlier¹. The isolation of all the compounds and the details of the investigation on the diterpenes are given. The mass spectra of the diterpenes are discussed.

ENHYDRA fluctuans Lour. (N.O. Compositae: tribe, *Heliantheae*), a small edible marshy shrub has been claimed to have antiinflammatory and various other uses in the Indian system of medicine^{2,3}. More recently, it has been shown to have high folic acid activity⁴. Chakravarti and Dutta⁵ reported the isolation of stigmasterol from this plant in 1952. As part of our programme for studies on indigenous plants, we undertook a thorough investigation of this species.

In a series of preliminary communications⁶⁻¹⁰, we reported the characterisation of a number of constituents from the whole plant. Since then, we have isolated another diterpene, (-)-kaur-15-en-19-oic acid and three more steroids along with β -amyrin and myristic acid. All the compounds isolated from this plant in this laboratory and by others¹¹⁻¹⁷ are listed in Table 1. In addition, isolation and characterisation of gibberellins A₉ and A₁₃ have been recently reported¹⁸. Detailed account of our work on the germacranolide lactones have already been published¹. The present paper deals with the isolation of all the other constituents (*vide* experimental) and the details of investigation on the diterpenes. The structures of the steroidal components form the subject matter of a separate communication¹⁹.

The characterisations⁶⁻⁸ of the known (-)-kaurane derivatives, namely, (-)-kaur-16-en-19-oic acid (I)^{20, 21}, (-)-kauran-16 α -ol (II)²², 16 α -hydroxy-(-)-kauran-19-oic acid (III)^{23, 24} and 15 α -hydroxy-(-)-kaur-16-en-19-oic acid (IV)²⁵⁻²⁷ were straight forward. Recently, we encountered another compound, m.p. 188°-90°, $[\alpha]_D -74.2^\circ$, identified as (-)-kaur-15-en-19-oic acid (V)²⁸. The structures III and V were further confirmed by their preparation from I involving acid catalysed hydration and rearrangement respectively²⁰.

Compound IV was found to be intimately associated with a new hydroxy acid (VI) which could only be resolved as its methyl ester (VIa), m.p. 134°, $[\alpha]_D -84.86^\circ$, and was characterised as such. The IR and NMR spectra (Table 2) of the compound⁹ indicated the presence of an axial carbomethoxy and a -CH=C-CH₂OH groupings. The latter function was supported by the chromic acid oxidation of the compound to an unstable single product, which appeared to be an $\alpha\beta$ -unsaturated aldehyde (ν_{max} 1680 cm⁻¹; λ_{max} 247 nm). When treated with methanolic hydrochloric acid at room temperature, a condition under which (-)-kaur-15-en-17-ol was reported²⁹ to have yielded the isomeric 16-en-15 α -ol by allylic rearrangement, VIa gave a mixture of products, none of which was found to be the expected rearranged alcohol (IVa). Two of the products obtained as oil, formed 2,4-DNP derivatives and presumably, are 17- or 15-oxo-derivatives. The third product, m.p. 190°-94° did not, however form a 2,4-DNP derivative. Its IR spectrum was very close to that of the starting alcohol (VIa), except that the OH stretching band was absent and an additional strong band appeared at 1085 cm⁻¹. This compound is presumably the methyl ether or a dimeric ether of VIa.

The structure and stereochemistry of VIa was finally proved by its osmium tetroxide hydroxylation to the triol VII also obtained from IVa by the same method (Scheme 1). The α -configuration of the 16-hydroxy group in VII has been assigned from the expected attack of the terminal double bond of IVa by the reagent from the less hindered side.

The diterpene esters IVb, C₂₅H₃₈O₄, m.p. 169°-70°, $[\alpha]_D -74.5^\circ$ and IVc, C₂₅H₃₆O₄, m.p. 193°-95°, obtained as an intimate mixture, could only be separated by tedious chromatography with infra-red

TABLE 1. COMPOUNDS ISOLATED FROM *E. fluctuans* LOUR.

No.	Compound	Ref.
<i>Germaeranolides</i>		
1.	Enhydrin	1, 6, 11; 15-17
2.	Fluctuadin	1
3.	Fluctuanin	1
<i>Diterpenes</i>		
4.	(-)-Kaur-16-en-19-oic acid ...	6, 13
5.	(-)-Kaur-15-en-19-oic acid ...	a
6.	(-)-Kauran-16 α -ol	6
7.	16 α -Hydroxy-(-)-kauran-19-oic acid ...	7, 14
8.	15 α -Hydroxy-(-)-kaur-16-en-19-oic acid	8
9.	15 α -Isovaleroyloxy-(-)kaur-16-en-19-oic acid	8
10.	15 α -Angeloyloxy-(-)-kaur-16-en-19-oic acid	8
11.	17-Hydroxy-(-)-kaur-15-en-19-oic acid ^b	9
<i>Triterpene</i>		
12.	β -Amyrin	a
<i>Steroids</i>		
13.	Stigmasterol	5, 6
14.	(24 <i>S</i>)-24-Ethyl-5, 22, 25-cholestatrien-3 β -ol	10, 17, 19
15.	(24 <i>S</i>)-24-Ethyl-5, 22, 25-cholestatrien-3 β -yl stearate... ..	19
16.	4, 22-Stigmastadien-3-one	19
17.	(24 <i>S</i>)-24-Ethyl-4,22,25-cholestatrien-3-one	19
<i>Others</i>		
18.	Myricyl alcohol	6
19.	Myristic acid	a
<p>a. Present report. b. Isolated as the methyl ester.</p>		

monitoring. Hydrolysis of both the compounds gave the same hydroxy acid IV. The two esters therefore, differ only with respect to the acyl functions (C₄H₉COO- in IVb and C₄H₇COO- in IVc). The NMR signal at δ 1.00 (doublet, J = 7 Hz), assignable to (CH₃)₂CH- indicated the presence of (CH₃)₂CH-CH₂-COO- grouping in IVb and a broad one-proton quartet (J = 7 Hz) at δ 6.13 and a singlet at δ 1.95 were compatible with a CH₃-CH = C(CH₃)COO- (angelate or tiglate) grouping in IVc. The assignments were corroborated by the mass spectra of the compounds (*vide infra*).

The structure IVb could be easily established by its preparation from isovaleric anhydride and IV but that of the angelate ester IVc could only be confirmed indirectly as in the sequel.

The tiglate (IVd) prepared from IV was found to be different from the natural product. The compound must then be the angelate ester of IV, a conclusion in accord with the upfield position of the vinylic proton resonance in the NMR spectrum³⁰. The angelate IVc itself however, could not be prepared, as condensation of angelic acid through its acid chloride with IV led to the tiglate IVd. The result is not unanticipated in view of the well-known facile acid and base catalysed isomerisation of angelic to tiglic acid. All the diterpene acids isolated from *E. fluctuans* have an axial COOH group at C-4 and the methyl esters Ia, IIIa, IVa, and VIa showed the C-O-C stretching band at \sim 1150 cm⁻¹ in the IR spectra in agreement with the earlier observation³¹.

Mass spectra: Studies on the mass spectral fragmentation of kaurenoid diterpenes are limited. The mass spectra of 16-hydroxy kaurenoid derivatives³² and kaurenolides³³ have been studied in some detail by Serebryakov *et al.* Caballero and Walls³⁴ have also reported the mass spectra of some kaurenoid derivatives. We now report some interesting features in the mass spectra of the isomeric Δ^{16} and Δ^{15} acids

TABLE 2. NMR DATA^a OF THE DITERPENES OF *E. fluctuans* LOUR.

Compound	4-Me	10-Me	13-H	15-H	17-H	Others
I	1.29	1.00	2.68 m	—	4.87 br (W _{1/2} = 7.5Hz)	—
II	0.85 0.88	1.07	—	—	1.38	—
III ^b	0.60	0.73	—	—	0.91	—
IV	1.28	1.00	2.78 m	3.88	5.18 5.30	—
IVb	1.28	1.00	2.83 m	5.20	5.20 5.37	1.00d (J = 7Hz), Me ₂ CH
IVc	1.27	1.00	2.82 m	5.13	5.13 5.43	1.95br, 2'-Me; 2.00 d (J = 7Hz), 3'-Me; 6.13 br q (J = 7Hz), 3'-H
V	1.24	0.98	—	5.08 br (W _{1/2} = 4.5Hz)	1.70d (J = 1.5Hz)	—
VIa	1.19	0.87	2.58 m	5.39 br (W _{1/2} = 3.5Hz)	4.22d (J = 1.5 Hz)	3.67, OMe

a. 60 MHz, in CDCl₃ solutions. Chemical shifts in δ units from internal TMS standard. Unmarked signals are singlets.
 b. In C₅D₈N.

I. R = H
Ia. R = Me

II. R = Me
III. R = COOH
IIIa. R = COOMe

IV. R = H

V. R = H

VI

IVb. R = COCH₂CHMe₂

VI. R = OH

IVc. R = COC^Z = CHMe
|
Me

IVd. R = COC^E = CHMe
|
Me

IVe. R = Ac

IVf. R = COCH = CMe₂

Scheme 1

Scheme 2

Scheme 3

Scheme 4

Scheme 5

Fig. 1

(I and V) and the corresponding 15- and 17-hydroxy acids (IV and VI) and some of their derivatives.

The mass spectra of the four compounds I, IV, V and VIa are reproduced in Figs. 1 and 2. All the compounds showed the expected loss of the C-10 angular methyl and C-4 carboxyl function. The mode of expulsion of the COOH group, however, seems to be dependant on other functionalities present in the molecule. Thus, though the compounds I, V and VIa showed loss of COOH(Me) from the molecular ion, the 15-hydroxy compound IV and its derivatives showed M-46 peaks corresponding to loss of HCOOH. The reason for this is not immediately clear. Another important fragmentation in case of the unsubstituted acids I and V seems to involve the loss of C-10 methyl along with C₂-C₃-C₄ fragment in ring A leading to the ion at *m/e* 187.

The most characteristic fragmentation in all the compounds, however, involves the strained bicyclo-octane system. This as to be expected as charge localisation at the C-15 or C-16 double bond should lead to facile cleavage of one of the bonds at C-8. However, considerable rearrangement of the molecular ion must be envisaged to rationalise the fragmentations. Thus the spectrum of I (Fig. 1) shows a prominent M-43 peak which must be due to the

loss of C₃H₇ radical, necessitating transfer of three hydrogens (probably 9-H, 11 β -H and 14-H) to the expelled C₁₅-C₁₆-C₁₇ unit (Scheme 2)*.

Similarly, the hydroxy acid IV (Scheme 3) showed the base peak at *m/e* 260 corresponding to the loss of C₃H₆O also requiring rearrangement of two hydrogen atoms.

When the hydroxy acid is acylated as in IVb and IVc (Scheme 4) the most intense peak observed in the high mass range is at *m/e* 300 corresponding to the loss of C₄H₉COOH and C₂H₇COOH respectively. That part of the *m/e* 300 peak arises by successive loss of ketene and water from the molecular ion is supported by the metastable peak for the process *m/e* 318 \rightarrow *m/e* 300. The low intensity of the *m/e* 260 peak showed that the loss of the C₁₅-C₁₆-C₁₇ moiety is not a favoured process in the esters, apparently due to the prior elimination of the C-15 oxygen function.

The fragmentation of the Δ^{15} compounds, V and VIa, considerably differs from that of the Δ^{16} compounds. The predominant feature in the spectrum

* A mechanism for this fragmentation has recently been suggested by Evans and Hanson³⁵ postulating transfer of 9-H, 12-H and 14-H. Whether 11-H or 12-H is involved in the rearrangement can however be settled only by appropriate labeling.

Fig. 2

of V is the peak at m/e 94 corresponding to $C_7H_{10}^+$ ion (species *b*) which might arise from the C/D ring, as it is shifted to m/e 110 in the hydroxy ester VIa. This assignment is supported by a peak at m/e 193 shifted to m/e 207 in VIa containing the A/B ring system (ion *a*) and derived from the M-15 ion with one hydrogen rearrangement. The hydroxy ester VIa also shows an intense M-H₂O peak which is presumably derived from the rearranged molecular ion.

Experimental

All m.p.s were determined in open capillaries in sulphuric acid bath and are uncorrected. Unless otherwise stated optical rotations were measured in CHCl₃ in a Hilger-Watts, M-511 Microptic photoelectric polarimeter. IR spectra were recorded in nujol mull with a Perkin Elmer Infra-cord (Model 137) spectrophotometer. Mass spectra were obtained from an MS-9 instrument at 70 eV using direct inlet system. Microanalyses were by Dr. R. D. Macdonald of Australian Microanalytical Service (CSIRO), Melbourne.

Unless otherwise stated silica gel for both column and thin layer chromatography are the products of M's. Gouri Chemicals, Calcutta. Petroleum ether refers to the fraction with b.p. 60°-80°.

Isolation of the constituents :

Dried and milled whole plant (4 kg) of *E. fluctuans* Lour. collected around Calcutta was extracted in a

Soxhlet apparatus with pet ether for 30 hr. The extract was concentrated to 150 ml and allowed to stand for two days, the separated solid was filtered and worked up for isolation of the sesquiterpenes¹. The filtrate was distilled and the residue (70 g) was chromatographed (6×45 cm) to yield the following crude fractions in order of elution.

Eluent	Fraction (wt)
Pet ether	A (10.4 g)
10% C ₆ H ₆ in pet ether	B (10.0 g)
20% " " " "	C (0.45 g)
50% " " " "	D (1.14 g)
50 to 75% " " " "	E (6.5 g)
C ₆ H ₆ to 10% MeOH in CHCl ₃	F (3.0 g)

Fraction A was rechromatographed and fractions A-1 to A-4 were obtained by elution with pet ether followed by 5, 10 and 20% benzene in pet ether

(24*S*)-24-Ethyl-5,22,25-cholestatrien-3β-yl stearate¹⁹ :

Fraction A-1 was macerated with acetone and the soluble part after chromatography and crystallisation from pet ether yielded needles (0.40 g) of (24*S*)-24-ethyl-5,22,25-cholestatrien-3β-yl stearate, m.p. 99°; [α]_D-25.5° (c 1.29); ν_{max} 1735 (C=O), 1640, 1655 (C=C), 965 (-CH=CH-*trans*) and 882 (=CH₂) cm⁻¹; NMR: δ 0.73s (18-Me), 1.08s (19-Me), 1.32s

$[-(\text{CH}_2)_n-]$, 1.71t ($J = 1.1$ Hz, 27-Me), 4.87m ($w_{\frac{1}{2}} = 3$ Hz, $= \text{CH}_2$) and 5.3-5.7 m (3-H and 5-H); mass spec. m/e 392 ($\text{M}-\text{C}_{17}\text{H}_{35}\text{COOH}$). (Found : C, 83.20; H, 11.82%. Calcd. for $\text{C}_{47}\text{H}_{80}\text{O}_2$: C, 83.37; H, 11.90%).

(-)-*Kaur-15-en-19-oic acid* (V) :

Fraction A-2, a crystalline mixture of two components was resolved by chromatography over AgNO_3 (5%) impregnated silica gel into (-)-*kaur-16-en-19-oic acid* (I, 1.8 g, *vide infra*) and (-)-*kaur-15-en-19-oic acid* (V, 0.44 g), m.p. $188^\circ\text{--}90^\circ$ (from pet ether); $[\alpha]_D -74.2^\circ$ (c 0.62); ν_{max} 3300-2550, 1680 (COOH), 818 ($= \text{CH}-$) cm^{-1} ; identified by direct comparison with a specimen prepared from I.

β -*Amyrin* :

Fraction A-3 on rechromatography and crystallisation from methanol yielded β -*amyrin* (0.42 g), m.p. $196^\circ\text{--}98^\circ$; acetate, m.p. $239^\circ\text{--}40^\circ$; identified by direct comparison with authentic specimens.

4,22-*Stigmastadien-3-one* and (24 *S*)-24-ethyl-4,22,25-*cholestatrien-3-one*¹⁹ :

Fraction A-4 on chromatography over neutral alumina yielded a crystalline mixture of two components which were separated by chromatography over AgNO_3 (5%) impregnated silica gel and crystallised from acetonitrile to yield 4,22-*stigmastadien-3-one*, m.p. 114° ; $[\alpha]_D +60.0^\circ$ (c 0.6); ν_{max} 1680, 1620 ($\text{C}=\text{C}=\text{O}$), 970 ($-\text{CH}=\text{CH}-$ *trans*) cm^{-1} ; $\lambda_{\text{max}}^{\text{EtOH}}$ 240 nm ($\log \epsilon$ 4.26); mass spec : m/e (rel. intensity) 410 (M^+ ; 68), 367 (41), 298 (42), 271 (64), 270 (31), 269(49), 229 (28); 124 (75) and 55 (100). (Found : C, 84.83; H, 11.30%. Calcd. for $\text{C}_{29}\text{H}_{48}\text{O}$: C, 84.81; H, 11.29%) and (24 *S*)-24-ethyl-4,22,25-*cholestatrien-3-one*, m.p. 104° , $[\alpha]_D +72.2^\circ$ (c 0.72); ν_{max} 1675, 1615 ($\text{C}=\text{C}=\text{O}$), 1645, 880 ($= \text{CH}_2$), 970 ($-\text{CH}=\text{CH}-$ *trans*) cm^{-1} ; $\lambda_{\text{max}}^{\text{EtOH}}$ 240 nm ($\log \epsilon$ 4.24); mass spec : m/e (rel. intensity) 408 (M^+ , 18), 379 (27), 299 (36), (98 (35), 271(48), 270 (40), 269 (100), 229 (12), 138 (29), 137 (40), 124 (22) and 109 (92). (Found : C, 85.09; H, 11.11%. Calcd. for $\text{C}_{29}\text{H}_{44}\text{O}$: C, 85.23; H, 10.85%).

(-)-*Kaur-16-en-19-oic acid* (I) :

Fraction B on crystallisation from pet ether afforded 6.0 g of (-)-*kaur-16-en-19-oic acid* (I), m.p. $176^\circ\text{--}78^\circ$; $[\alpha]_D -109^\circ$ (c 0.46, EtOH) {lit.²⁰ m.p. $179^\circ\text{--}81^\circ$; $[\alpha]_D -110^\circ$ }; ν_{max} 3000-2600, 1700 (COOH), 1660, 875 ($= \text{CH}_2$) cm^{-1} .

The methyl ester (Ia) prepared with CH_2N_2 crystallised from pet ether in needles, m.p. 89° ; $[\alpha]_D -102^\circ$ (c 0.6) {lit.²⁰ m.p. $88^\circ\text{--}89^\circ$; $[\alpha]_D -107^\circ$ }; ν_{max} 1720, 1140 (COOMe), 1650 and 870 ($= \text{CH}_2$) cm^{-1} .

Concentration of the mother liquors of I yielded myricyl alcohol (0.8 g.).

(-)-*Kauran-16 α -ol* (II) :

Crystallisation of *Fraction C* from CHCl_3 -MeOH yielded needles of (-)-*kauran-16 α -ol* (II), m.p. $215^\circ\text{--}16^\circ$; $[\alpha]_D -45.2^\circ$ (c 0.4) {lit.²² m.p. $214^\circ\text{--}16^\circ$.

$[\alpha]_D -45^\circ$ }; ν_{max} 3275 (OH) cm^{-1} ; mass spec. m/e 290 (M^+). (Found : C, 82.40; H, 11.69; O, 4.84%. Calcd. for $\text{C}_{20}\text{H}_{34}\text{O}$: C, 82.69; H, 11.80; O, 5.51%).

Stigmasterol and (24*S*)-24-ethyl-5,22,25-*cholestatrien-3 β -ol*¹⁹ :

Fraction D was a mixture of two components which could not be resolved by chromatography and was therefore acetylated ($\text{Ac}_2\text{O}/\text{Py}$) and chromatographed over silica gel impregnated with AgNO_3 (5%). One of the acetates crystallised from methanol in flakes, m.p. $149^\circ\text{--}50^\circ$; $[\alpha]_D -46.6^\circ$ (c 0.82); mass spec. m/e 392 ($\text{M}-\text{CH}_3\text{COOH}$). (Found : C, 82.01; H, 11.13%. Calcd. for $\text{C}_{31}\text{H}_{48}\text{O}_2$: C, 82.24; H, 10.69%). Saponification of the compound yielded (24 *S*)-24-ethyl-5,22,25-*cholestatrien-3 β -ol*, m.p. 154° (from alcohol); $[\alpha]_D -44.0^\circ$ (c 0.5); mass spec. m/e 410 (M^+). (Found : C, 83.55; H, 11.29%; Calcd. for $\text{C}_{29}\text{H}_{46}\text{O} \cdot \frac{1}{2}\text{C}_2\text{H}_5\text{OH}$: C, 83.08; H, 11.39%).

This compound was identical (m.p., m.m.p., TLC, IR and $[\alpha]_D$) with a sample obtained earlier from *Alangium lamarckii* Thw.¹⁰

The other acetate was found to be stigmasteryl acetate, m.p. $144^\circ\text{--}45^\circ$; $[\alpha]_D -56.5^\circ$ (c 0.6), confirmed by direct comparison of the sterol and its benzoate with authentic samples.

Isovalerate (IVb) and *angelate* (IVc) of 15 α -hydroxy-(-)-*kaur-16-en-19-oic acid* :

Fraction E on crystallisation yielded a sharp melting (173°) compound that appeared to be homogeneous from a single spot in TLC. The mass spectrum however indicated it to be a mixture of two compounds which was resolved by repeated chromatography over silica gel with IR monitoring to yield after crystallisation from pet ether-benzene the *isovalerate* (IVb) and the *angelate* (IVc) of 15 α -hydroxy-(-)-*kaur-16-en-19-oic acid*.

IVb : m.p. $169^\circ\text{--}70^\circ$; $[\alpha]_D -74.5^\circ$ (c 0.6); ν_{max} 3100-2600 and 1697 (COOH), 1735 and 1180 (COOR) cm^{-1} . (Found : C, 74.7; H, 9.41%. Calcd. for $\text{C}_{25}\text{H}_{38}\text{O}_4$: C, 74.59; H, 9.51%).

IVc : m.p. $193^\circ\text{--}95^\circ$; ν_{max} 3000-2600 and 1695 (COOH), 1700, 1650, 1230 and 1160 (*angelate*)³⁶ cm^{-1} . (Found : C, 74.62; H, 9.27%. Calcd. for $\text{C}_{25}\text{H}_{36}\text{O}_4$: C, 74.96; H, 9.06%).

Myristic acid, 17-hydroxy-(-)-*kaur-15-en-19-oic acid* (IV), 15 α -hydroxy-(-)-*kaur-16-en-19-oic acid* (IV) and 16 α -hydroxy-(-)-*kauran-19-oic acid* (III) :

Fraction F was rechromatographed. (i) *Fraction F-1* eluted with 75% C_6H_6 in pet ether followed by C_6H_6 was taken up in ether and extracted with 5% Na_2CO_3 soln. The aqueous extract was acidified, extracted with CH_2Cl_2 and evaporated. The residue on crystallisation from alcohol yielded *myristic acid* (1.4 g.), m.p. 58° , identified by comparison of the infra-red spectrum³⁷.

(ii) *Fraction F-2* eluted with CHCl_3 , on crystallisation from C_6H_6 -MeOH yielded a mixture (0.35 g) of 17-hydroxy-(-)-*kaur-15-en-19-oic acid* (VI) and 15 α -hydroxy-(-)-*kaur-16-en-19-oic acid* (IV) which could

not be resolved by chromatography either as such or as their acetates. The mixture was methylated with CH_2N_2 and carefully chromatographed. Elution with 3 to 5% ether in pet ether yielded first methyl 15 α -hydroxy-(—)-kaur-16-en-19-oate (IVa, *vide infra*) and then methyl 17-hydroxy-(—)-kaur-15-en-19-oate (VIa), crystallised from pet ether in needles, m.p. 134°; $[\alpha]_D -84.86^\circ$ (c 0.66); ν_{max} 3300 (OH), 1730, 1158 (COOMe) and 825 (=CH—) cm^{-1} . (Found: C, 75.63; H, 9.84%. Calcd. for $\text{C}_{21}\text{H}_{32}\text{O}_3$: C, 75.86; H, 9.71%).

(iii) Fraction F-3 eluted with 2% MeOH in CHCl_3 crystallised from C_6H_6 -MeOH to yield 16 α -hydroxy-(—)-kauran-19-oic acid (III, 0.63 g), m.p. 276°–78°; $[\alpha]_D -117^\circ$ (c 0.53 in $\text{C}_5\text{H}_5\text{N}$); ν_{max} 3400 (OH), 2700–2600 and 1697 (COOH) cm^{-1} ; mass spec. (Ref. 7). (Found: C, 74.61; H, 9.77%. Calcd. for $\text{C}_{20}\text{H}_{32}\text{O}_3$: C, 74.94; H, 10.07%).

Methylation of III with diazomethane followed by crystallisation from pet ether yielded the methyl ester IIIa, m.p. 155°; $[\alpha] -101.5^\circ$ (c 1.0, MeOH); ν_{max} 3350 (OH), 1720 and 1160 (COOMe) cm^{-1} . (Found: C, 75.28; H, 10.36%. Calcd. for $\text{C}_{21}\text{H}_{34}\text{O}_3$: C, 75.40; H, 10.25%).

Preparation of III and V from I:

To a solution of I (1 g) in acetone (30 ml) was added 2N HCl (10 ml) and the mixture refluxed for 2 hr²⁰. The reaction mixture was cooled, the separated solid filtered and crystallised from C_6H_6 -MeOH, when III (0.55 g), identical in all respects with the natural product, was obtained.

The filtrate was concentrated under reduced pressure and taken up in CHCl_3 . The residue obtained in the usual way was chromatographed over AgNO_3 (5%) impregnated silica gel yielding unconverted starting material (0.2 g) followed by 0.15 g of V, m.p. 188°–90°, identical with the natural product.

Hydrolysis of IVb and IVc to IV:

Compound IVb (0.2 g) was hydrolysed by refluxing in 5% alc. KOH (25 ml) soln. Usual work up followed by crystallisation from C_6H_6 - CHCl_3 gave IV (0.12 g) as flakes, m.p. 227°–28°; $[\alpha]_D -120.5^\circ$ (c 0.83); ν_{max} 3340 (OH), 3200–2550, 1695 (COOH), 895 (=CH₂) cm^{-1} . (Found: C, 75.17; H, 9.32%. Calcd. for $\text{C}_{20}\text{H}_{30}\text{O}_3$: C, 75.42; H, 9.5%). Similar hydrolysis of IVc (50 mg) also afforded IV (31 mg).

Treatment of IV with diazomethane in ether yielded the methyl ester IVa, crystallised from pet ether in needles, m.p. 101°; $[\alpha]_D -101.5^\circ$ (c 0.66); ν_{max} 3520 (OH), 1720, 1150 (COOMe), 1660, 915 (=CH₂) cm^{-1} . Acetylation of IV with Ac_2O - $\text{C}_5\text{H}_5\text{N}$ and crystallisation from pet ether furnished the acetate IVe, m.p. 166°–69°; $[\alpha]_D -86^\circ$ (c 0.8); identical (m.m.p., IR) with an authentic sample of 15 α -acetoxy-(—)-kaur-16-en-19-oic acid, kindly supplied by Prof. C. H. Brieskorn^{25, 26}.

Oxidation of IV to 15-oxo-(—)kaur-16-en-19-oic acid (VIII):

To a solution of IV (30 mg) in acetone (1 ml) was added Jones' reagent (0.1 ml) at 0°. The mixture was stirred for 5 min, diluted with water (1 ml), benzene (10 ml) was added, stirred for 5 min and allowed to stand. The benzene layer was separated, washed, dried and evaporated. The residue on chromatography followed by crystallisation from ether-pet ether yielded needles (16 mg) of VIII, m.p. 195°–201°; $[\alpha]_D -130^\circ$ (c 0.8) {lit.^{21, 23} m.p. 197°–201°, $[\alpha]_D -181^\circ$; m.p. 193°–94°, $[\alpha]_D -122^\circ$ }; ν_{max} 3100–2600, 1680 (COOH), 1720, 1640 (cyclopentenone); λ_{max}^{EtOH} 233 (ϵ 6,100) nm.

Preparation of the β : β -dimethyl acrylate IVf:

β : β -Dimethyl acrylic acid (0.3 g) was heated on steam bath with thionyl chloride (0.4 ml) for 1 hr and the excess thionyl chloride removed. To the cooled acid chloride in benzene (1 ml) was added a benzene solution (1 ml) of IV (20 mg) and two drops of pyridine. The mixture was refluxed for one hour, cooled, diluted with benzene (10 ml) and stirred with 0.5 ml of HCl (1:1). The benzene layer was separated, washed, dried and evaporated when an oily residue was obtained. Water (10 ml) was added to the oil and allowed to evaporate on steam bath. The semicrystalline solid on chromatography and crystallisation from pet ether yielded 16 mg of the β : β -dimethylacrylate (IVf) as prisms, m.p. 205°–208°, ν_{max} 3300–2550 and 1690 (COOH), 1705, 1655, 1220, 1140, 1075 and 852 (β : β -dimethyl acrylate) and 905 (=CH₂) cm^{-1} . (Found: C, 74.86; H, 9.08%. Calcd. for $\text{C}_{25}\text{H}_{36}\text{O}_4$: C, 74.96; H, 9.06%).

Preparation of the tiglate IVd:

Acylation of IV (25 mg) with tigloyl chloride (from 100 mg of tiglic acid) similarly gave the tiglate IVd (14 mg), crystallised from pet ether in needles, m.p. 198°, ν_{max} 3400–2550 and 1700 (COOH), 1700, 1650, 1255, 1130, 1075 and 732 (tiglate)³⁶ and 900 (=CH₂) cm^{-1} . (Found: C, 74.71; H, 9.10%. Calcd. for $\text{C}_{25}\text{H}_{36}\text{O}_4$: C, 74.96; H, 9.06%).

Attempted preparation of angelate IVc:

Acylation of IV (25 mg) with angelic acid (100 mg) under aforesaid conditions yielded a product identical (m.p. and IR) with the tiglate IVd.

Preparation of isovalerate IVb:

A mixture of IV (30 mg) in C_6H_6 (1 ml), pyridine (2 drops) and iso-valeric acid anhydride (0.1 ml) was heated on steam bath for 1 hr, cooled, cold dil. HCl (2 ml) added and then extracted with benzene. The benzene extract on usual work-up gave an oily residue to which water (10 ml) was added and allowed to evaporate on steam bath. Repetition of the process furnished a crystalline solid which was recrystallised from aq. alcohol to yield the isovalerate IVb (16 mg) as colourless needles, m.p. 166°–68°, identical (m.m.p. $[\alpha]_D$ and IR) with the natural product.

Preparation of methyl 15 α , 16 α , 17-trihydroxy-(-)-kauran-19-oate (VII) :

(i) To a solution of IVa (11 mg) in pyridine (0.1 mg) was added OsO₄ (15 mg) and the mixture stirred for 3 hr. A solution of sodium bisulphite (56 mg) in water (1.5 ml) containing pyridine (1 ml) was added and the mixture stirred again for 15 min. It was then extracted with benzene, the extract washed with water and the pyridine removed by shaking with Amberlite-IR 120 resin (H⁺ form). Evaporation of the solvent followed by crystallisation from C₆H₆-MeOH yielded VII (10 mg) as needles, m.p. 202°-203°; ν_{max} 3300-3200 (OH), 1725 (COOMe) cm⁻¹. (Found : C, 69.02; H, 8.1%. Calcd. for C₂₁H₃₂O₅ : C, 69.19; H, 8.85%).

(ii) Similar hydroxylation of VIa (6 mg) with OsO₄ (10 mg) and identical work up yielded VII (5 mg), identical (m.m.p., IR) with the sample obtained from IVa.

Chromic acid oxidation of VIa :

To a solution of VIa (8 mg) in CH₂Cl₂ (2 ml) was added a solution (0.1 ml) of pyridine-CrO₃ complex³⁸ in CH₂Cl₂ and the mixture stirred for 2 hr. Usual work up gave an unstable oily material which was homogeneous by TLC but could not be crystallised. A freshly purified (filtration of pet ether solution through silica gel) sample showed, ν_{max}^{film} 1725 (COOMe) and 1680 (α , β -unsaturated aldehyde) and λ_{max}^{EtOH} at 247 nm.

Acid rearrangement²⁶ of VIa :

(i) To a solution of VIa (10 mg) in MeOH (5 ml) was added conc. HCl (0.25 ml) and the mixture allowed to stand (r.t.) for 20 hr. The reaction mixture was diluted with ether (26 ml), washed with dil. Na₂CO₃ solution and then with water, dried and evaporated. The residue in TLC showed in addition to unconverted material, the presence of two less polar major components. No spot corresponding to IVa could be detected. The two components were separated by chromatography and both gave positive test for carbonyl group with 2,4-DNP. Another component was obtained crystalline, m.p. 190°-94°; ν_{max} 1725, 1140 (COOMe), 1085 and 1025 cm⁻¹.

(ii) Repetition of the experiment with lower concentration of HCl in MeOH or HClO₄ in 80% aq. THF and TLC analysis of the reaction mixtures showed variations only in the amount of the starting material consumed, otherwise the same products as mentioned above were obtained and in no case formation of IVa could be detected.

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